

A FOT PREDICTION PROCEDURE FOR HF COMMUNICATIONS FREQUENCY MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Use of the ionospheric sounder as an aid in HF frequency management has proved to be more successful than the use of ionospheric models, but the disadvantages of cost, airwave pollution, and cumbersomeness of operation prevent its direct, routine use on most communications paths. Instead, we believe that results nearly as good can be obtained with models which are updated by "recent" sounder measurements made on a "nearby" path. The exact meanings of "recent" and "nearby" depend, respectively, on the temporal and spatial correlation of ionospheric properties over long periods of time and over large geographical regions. We describe here the measurement of correlation of Maximum Observable Frequencies, and show how the results may be used to predict the Frequency of Optimum Transmission (FOT) on a path distant from the sounded path.

INTRODUCTION

The traditional tool for HF frequency-management decision-making has been the use of ionospheric models to predict propagation effects. Many such models have been developed; they differ widely in their complexity, range of applicability, and the directness with which their output is applicable to the frequency manager's needs (for example, they might predict ionospheric density profiles, or they might predict the MOF directly). While such predictive models may represent well the average ionosphere, they do not represent the short-term (1-24 hour) fluctuations in ionospheric parameters as well as desired.

More recently, sounders have been used to make direct measurements of propagation conditions on specific communications paths. The vertical-incidence sounder (VIS) and oblique-incidence sounder (OIS) each has its advantages, and both are capable of measuring the short-term fluctuations which models cannot provide. The main drawbacks to their wide-spread use are cost, pollution of the airwaves, and cumbersomeness of operation.

Because of the deficiencies in both models and sounders, attempts are now being made to combine the two techniques, so that the model will represent the mean values of ionospheric properties, and real-time sounder measurements will adjust the model predictions for short-term variations. The goal is to produce MOF predictions with an accuracy approaching that of sounder measurements, and with convenience

approaching that of model calculations.

The purpose of this report is to discuss measurements of the correlation of ionospheric parameters measured on two paths separated in space or time, and to derive one of the numerous applications of these measurements: a procedure for using the MOF measured on a sounded path to forecast the highest frequency on another path which, with a specified probability, will not exceed the MOF on that path. This frequency is called the Frequency of Optimum Transmission, or FOT. To illustrate these techniques, data taken from the Solid Shield experiment, a test of HF communication procedures in the Eastern United States, are used.

MOF CORRELATION

Correlation Parameter

While the MOF is considered the single most useful ionospheric parameter for practical purposes, one cannot directly correlate MOF's at different positions on the earth because of the MOF's well-known dependence on latitude and time of day (Rush 1976). Instead, we adopt a MOF-prediction model which incorporates the effects of geographical position and time of day, and look for some parameter which can be adjusted to make the predicted MOF equal the real (i.e., measured) MOF. The MINIMUF model (Rose et al, 1978a,b) was chosen because it is easy to use, reasonably accurate, and has enjoyed considerable success in frequency management operations. MINIMUF uses a single parameter, the solar 10.7 cm flux, to account for solar effects on the ionosphere. We now use the 10.7 cm flux parameter as an adjustable parameter which is used to force MINIMUF to give the measured MOF value. This effective 10.7 cm flux, or simply "effective flux", thereby loses its literal meaning. It is (in principle) independent of geographical position and of time of day, however, and is therefore suitable as a parameter which can be compared from path to path.

Correlation of Effective Fluxes on a Pair of Paths

To illustrate the correlation of effective fluxes for a pair of paths we use data from the Solid Shield experiment. These data were chosen because of the relatively large quantity of data available: there are 1604 MOF measurements, covering 401 hours of sounder operation spread over 17 days. MOF's were measured on the six

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paths illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 2 illustrates three examples of effective-flux comparison for a particular pair of paths: MacDill to Norfolk, and Lejeune to Norfolk. Each of the three plots refers to data acquired during a specific hour of each of a number of days. In Figure 2a, for example, the nine data points refer to data acquired between 0700 and 0800Z on each of nine days. Figures 2a, 2b, and 2c were chosen to illustrate situations in which the correlation is, respectively, about average, a little better than in most, and worse than in most situations.

For each of the plots in Figure 2 a linear regression line in the form

$$Y = a + b X \quad (1)$$

was calculated, where X and Y measure the effective fluxes on the Lejeune - Norfolk and MacDill - Norfolk paths, respectively. The fitted line may be used with MINIMUMUF for forecasting, since a measured MOF and the derived effective flux on the Lejeune - Norfolk path lead, through equation 1, to an effective flux and then to a MINIMUMUF MOF prediction on the MacDill - Norfolk path.

In some correlation plots it was noticed that one or two "wild" points resulted in a linear regression line with a slope differing greatly from the expected slope of $\sim 45^\circ$. Therefore, we have in some cases processed the data twice, first using all the data, and then eliminating by subjective exclusion up to three points per plot.

The correlation of effective fluxes on a pair of paths can be measured quantitatively by the correlation coefficient r. Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be n values of effective flux measured for path 1 at the times t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n . Let Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_n be the values of effective flux measured for path 2 at the same times. The correlation of the effective fluxes on the two paths is defined by the correlation coefficient r:

$$r = \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^n X_i Y_i - (\sum_{i=1}^n X_i) (\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i)}{\sqrt{n \sum_{i=1}^n X_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n X_i)^2} \sqrt{n \sum_{i=1}^n Y_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i)^2}}$$

Thus defined, the correlation coefficient measures the degree of linear relationship between the variables X and Y, and is independent of the units in which the variables are measured. A useful interpretation is that

$$r^2 = \frac{\text{Variation in Y explained by linear model}}{\text{Total variation observed in Y}}$$

The quantity r^2 is known as the coefficient of determination.

Time Variation of Correlation Coefficient

We have computed the correlation coefficient as a function of time for eighteen combinations of the six paths involved in the Solid Shield project. Some of the results are shown in Figure 3. For most pairs of paths there are two plots: one uses all the data, and the other uses data from which "wild points" have been discarded.

MOF FORECASTS

We consider three ways to forecast the MOF, all of them using MINIMUMUF:

1. MINIMUMUF alone
2. MINIMUMUF updated by sounder measurements on the same path
3. MINIMUMUF updated by sounder measurements on a different path.

Forecasting by MINIMUMUF Alone

Given a specified communications path, day of year, and solar 10.7 cm flux value, the MINIMUMUF model predicts the MOF as a function of time of day. There is some debate about the most appropriate value of solar flux to use; in some cases the daily value (as broadcast hourly by WWV) seems to work well, while in other cases a value equal to the flux averaged over the previous five days is preferred. To continue with data from the Solid Shield Test (Lejeune - Norfolk path, 3-19 May 1981), we have calculated the MINIMUMUF MOF predictions and compared them with the observed MOFs. These data include approximately 350 hours of measurements spanning a period of 17 days. The rms error of these forecasts (2.49 MHz when the daily solar flux value was used, and 2.64 MHz when the five-day average was used) are shown in Figure 4. Since the MINIMUMUF forecast changes only once per day, the rms error is independent of the delay between the times of forecasting and measurement, for times up to 24 hours. Thus, the MINIMUMUF-alone rms error appears as a horizontal line in Figure 4.

Forecasting by the Updated MINIMUMUF Model

The prospect of improving forecasting accuracy by "updating" is based on the presumption of low-frequency ($f \leq 1 \text{ day}^{-1}$) variations in the MOF which are not accounted for in the MINIMUMUF model. If MINIMUMUF forecasts are made with the effective flux which forces MINIMUMUF to give a MOF which agrees with the measured value, then it seems reasonable to expect these forecasts for at least the near future to be better than with the un-updated MINIMUMUF. Effective flux determinations may be made whether on the path for which the forecast is desired, or on some other path. When using an effective flux measured on a path different from the path on which the forecast is desired, it is necessary to use a correlation function similar to those illustrated in Figure 2 to determine the effective flux on the path for which predictions are being made.

Figure 4 shows the rms error between forecast and measured MOFs on the Lejeune - Norfolk path as a function of the time delay

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between forecast and measurement. One curve results from predictions using effective flux measurements from the same path. The calculations for this curve include all data for that path for which both forecast and measurement (within 24 hours) were possible. In this case, the correlation measurements are not involved. The other two curves are derived from forecasts based on effective fluxes measured on two other paths: Driver - Ft. Bragg, and MacDill - Ft. Bragg. In these cases, the corresponding effective fluxes for the Lejeune-Norfolk path were determined from correlation plots of the type illustrated in Figure 2. These curves must be considered a demonstration rather than a fair test of the technique because the forecasts were based on effective flux correlations derived from the same data. An effective test of the technique will require data acquired over a larger period of time.

FREQUENCY MANAGER'S MUF-FORECASTING PROCEDURE

Management of an HF communications network demands the assignment of frequencies in such a way that the requirements of connectivity, data rates, covertness, etc., are achieved. Here we are concerned with only one of the constraints to the assignment process: the requirement that assigned frequencies be at or below the MOF for the assigned communications path. Given a measurement of MOF on a sounded path, we attempt to produce a procedure for determining, with a pre-determined probability of success, the highest frequency which does not exceed the MOF on the communications path. Such a frequency may be called the Frequency of Optimum Transmission, or FOT. So defined, it is not a single quantity, since it depends on the specified probability. We thus speak, for example, of the "90% FOT" for a given path and time, meaning the highest frequency which, with 90% probability, will be below the actual MOF. The minimum acceptable probability for a deployable communication system depends on the application, but would typically be 80 - 95%.

Probability Interval of an Effective Flux Forecast

When the correlation of effective fluxes on a pair of paths is known, as illustrated in Figure 2, the linear regression fix (equation 1) can be used to infer the effective flux on one path when the effective flux on the other path has been measured. This is not an appropriate effective flux to use for frequency-management purposes however, because there is a 50% probability that the MOF calculated with this effective flux will exceed the actual MOF. Satisfactory communications require a higher probability of success. We therefore consider the probable errors associated with these forecasts an effective flux.

We consider the n measurements X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n of effective flux on one path, and the corresponding measurements Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_n of effective flux on the second path. Forecasts of effective flux on the second (now considered the unknown) path are given by $F = a + bX$, where

X is the current measured effective flux on the first (or control) path. For values of control path effective flux near the mean value:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n X_i$$

the standard error of forecast in the corresponding values of F is

$$s_e = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-2} \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - F_i)^2}$$

where $F_i = a + b X_i$ is the linear regression estimate of F corresponding to the control path effective flux X_i . For values of control path effective flux X not near the mean the standard error of forecast is somewhat greater:

$$s_f = s_e \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{n} + \frac{(X - \bar{X})^2}{\sum (X_i - \bar{X})^2}}$$

The errors in forecasting effective flux from the linear regression formula are expected to follow a t-distribution with $v = n-2$ degrees of freedom. The probability that the actual effective flux will depart from the estimated value F by the amount t is given by P (t, v), a function which can be either computed or read from a table (see Harnett 1982). The normalized variable t is the effective flux measured in units of the standard error of forecast s_f . Thus a C% confidence interval for the actual flux may be defined by the extremes

$$F \pm t_{c,v} S_f,$$

where

$t_{c,v}$ is the number for which

$$\int_{-t_{c,v}}^{+t_{c,v}} P(t,v) dt = C/100$$

Figure 5 illustrates the application of this procedure to the correlation data collected on eleven days in the time interval 0300 - 0400Z on the two Solid Shield paths MacDill - Norfolk and Lejeune - Norfolk. The correlation between the effective flux F on the MacDill - Norfolk path to the effective flux X on the Lejeune - Norfolk path is expressed by the linear regression line

$$\hat{F} = 28.88 + 0.831 X$$

The 80, 90 and 95 percent confidence intervals calculated by the above equations are also plotted. Thus, for example, a measured effective flux of 200 on the control path (Lejeune - Norfolk) results in a best estimate for the effective flux on the MacDill - Norfolk path of 137.3, with an 80% probability that the actual effective flux will be between 118 and 157 and a 95% probability that it will fall between 106 and 169.

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FOT Forecasting Procedure

The MINIMUF program may be used to transform the forecasts of effective flux and confidence intervals on the MacDill - Norfolk path (Fig. 5) into FOT forecasts, thereby making the data more readily useable for frequency-management purposes (see Figure 6). In transforming the effective flux forecasts, only the linear regression line and the lower limits of the probability intervals are retained and their labels are changed to correspond to a new interpretation. The new curves represent the most probable value for the MOF, and the frequencies which are expected to be below the actual MOF with probabilities of 90%, 95%, and 97.5%. The latter curves are thus labeled as "FOT" (Frequencies of Optimum Transmission), and the most probable MOF curve is now the "50% FOT". This set of information should be of more assistance in selecting a propagating frequency than a single value of MUF whose relation to the variance in the expected MOF is unknown.

REFERENCES

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Figure 1: Map of southeastern US showing propagation paths and placement of sounder transmitters (T) and receivers (R) during the Solid Shield program.

Figure 2: Three examples of correlation of effective fluxes on the MacDill-Norfolk and LeJeune-Norfolk paths. An "effective flux" is the 10.7 cm solar flux for which the MINIMUF MUF prediction equals an observed MUF.

Figure 3: Correlation coefficient, as a function of diurnal time, measuring the correlation of effective fluxes for three of the eighteen pairs of Solid Shield propagation paths.

Figure 5: Confidence intervals in the prediction of effective flux on the MacDill to Norfolk path in the time interval 0300Z-0400Z, using MINIMUF updated with Lejeune to Norfolk data. Given a measurement of effective flux on the Lejeune to Norfolk path the three pairs of curves represent the intervals within which the MacDill to Norfolk effective flux may be expected to fall with probabilities of 80, 90, and 95 percent.

Figure 4: RMS error between measured MOFs on the Lejeune to Norfolk path and MOFs predicted by a variety of techniques, as a function of time delay between prediction and measurement.

Figure 6: Curves for forecasting the Frequency of Optimum Transmission on the MacDill to Norfolk path for the hour 0300Z-0400Z. Given a measurement of effective flux on the Lejeune to Norfolk path, the three lower curves are guides for determining a frequency with a specified probability that this frequency will be at or below the actual MOF.

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